

Fragments in the Ruins: Decolonising the frame

by Dr Hiya Deb (she/her)

Hiya Deb is a researcher and filmmaker working across a range of formats. She completed her PhD in Media and Communications at Goldsmiths, University of London. Her practice-based research focused on Dalit refugee narratives and transgenerational trauma through creative documentary filmmaking. Her work explores how visual storytelling can function as a powerful tool for healing and representation. Her film 'Katatar', which examines Dalit refugee experiences, was shortlisted in the doctoral category for the BAFTSS Practice Research Awards.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18925548

I remember the silence first. It filled the porch of an elderly woman's home in a resettlement colony outside Kolkata, one of those unmarked bureaucratic corners of the city that rarely appear on maps. She had agreed to speak with me about her migratory journey from Khulna after the Partition. As I adjusted the lens on my camera, she turned away and murmured – "*Ei shob golpo bolt ichhe kore na*" (I don't feel like telling these stories). This was not the silence of forgetting. It was the silence of caste and discrimination. A refusal, shaped by decades of social exclusion, to participate in a narrative economy that had historically devalued her pain.

I am a non-Dalit, Bengali 'Savarna' (upper caste) woman researcher and filmmaker working within the traditions of visual anthropology and creative documentary. That silence marked the beginning of a slow unlearning. In this essay, I explore how ethnographic filmmaking with Dalit refugee community challenges dominant narratives. Through fragments of memory, silence and embodied survival, these women expose the violent unevenness of the crisis. My project began with an aim to document Dalit refugee narratives, stories I noticed were consistently absent from dominant representation of Partition in Bengali cinema, literature and public history. Films like Ritwik Ghatak's *Subarnarekha* (1965) had shaped my early understanding of migration and trauma. But they offered little insight into how caste-inflected displacement. Where were the refugees who did not settle in Kolkata's '*bhadralok*' neighbourhoods but were pushed to the peripheries, to the margins of the margin?

Over two years of fieldwork, I met families who had been relocated to canal embankments or the outskirts of Kolkata or in remote forest areas in India before gaining housing. The spaces of their stories were subtle, outside formal archives, resistant to the linearity of historical timelines. Memory here was transmitted through gestures, poetry, folk songs, cooking and the trembling repetition of dates that didn't align with records. Visual anthropology teaches us to be attentive not only to what we see but the conditions under which we are allowed to see. The camera is never neutral. Inspired by scholars like Trinh Minh-ha (1991), I moved from "capturing" images to creating spaces for relational storytelling. Sometimes, this meant filmi hands making food, and other times, it meant not filming at all. These were methodological choices shaped by ethics, not efficiency. I used creative documentary as a methodological tool within visual anthropology to explore how transgenerational trauma among Dalit refugees is both inherited and navigated through embodied memory, silence and everyday survival.

Figure 1. Still from the 'Katatar' (Barbed Wire), directed by the author. Videos captured by Pabitra Kumar Khosla and Sunil Padhi.

In the low-lying outskirts of Kolkata, I met Geeta Das, a woman in her 70s migrated from the present-day Bangladesh as a child along with her mother after the Partition. During our conversation, she laughed bitterly and pointed to her surroundings to show the poor living condition. She said, "Our condition has not changed. Only the government has. We have always been at their mercy". As a non-Dalit filmmaker, I had to learn to sit and to allow for footage that was not "visually rich" in conventional terms, but held the texture of lived survival. I found that moments of stillness carried more meaning than explanatory interviews. This counter-archive is not meant to replace official narratives but to coexist as friction. It is a reminder that history does not flow in a straight line and that visual anthropology must learn to navigate what Lila Abu-Lughod (1996) calls "ethnographies of the particular". We do not speak for 'others', we dwell with them in partial connection. Counter-memory as theorised by Foucault (1977), refers to the act of remembering against the grain of official narratives. In the context of Dalit refugee cinema, counter-memory involves reclaiming silenced histories through visual storytelling that is affective, situated and dialogic. This demands a shift from objectifying subjects to co-creating meaning through collaborative methods, where the camera becomes a conduit of relationality rather than surveillance.

This ethnographic journey has reshaped how I think of documentary film, not as a mode of explanation but as an act of relation. It is an invitation to witness, not conclude. For me, the ethics of visual anthropology lie not in the precision of footage, but in the care of encounter. And for the Dalit refugees with whom I worked, visual storytelling became not a mirror but a medium that could hold fragments of memory, grief and survival without demanding coherence or closure. In a time marked by crises and rising authoritarianism, decolonising the frame is not simply about who holds the camera, but how we see, what we refuse to see and whose stories we learn to honour, not for us, but with us.

Figures 3 and 4. Stills from the 'Katatar' (Barbed Wire), directed by the author. Book of poems by a Dalit refugee who migrated after the Partition of India. Videos captured by Pabitra Kumar Khosla and Sunil Padhi.

A decolonised visual anthropology does not merely expand the archive of representation but transforms the ethical foundations of the discipline. It requires a move from hierarchical observation to horizontal collaboration. In the context of caste and displacement this transformation is urgent and necessary. Dalit refugee cinema when shaped through the 'Dalit Gaze' would offer a powerful counterpoint to dominant narratives. It would invite viewers to reckon with histories of violence that continue to shape the present and to imagine alternative futures rooted in justice and dignity.

Figure 4. Still from the 'Katatar' (Barbed Wire), directed by the author. Videos captured by Pabitra Kumar Khosla and Sunil Padhi.

Bibliography

'*Subarnarekha*' (film). (1965). Directed by Ritwik Ghatak.

Minh-ha, T.T. (1991). *When the Moon Waxes Red*. Routledge.

Abu-Lughod, L., (1996). '*Writing Against Culture*', In Richard G. Fox (ed.), *Recapturing Anthropology: Working in the Present*. School of American Research Press. pp. 137-162.

Foucault, M. (1977). *Language, counter-memory, practice: selected essays and interviews*. Cornell University Press.

© Anthways 2026

[Accessibility statement](#)

[Cookie use](#)